

Design of Optical Phased Array Beam Steering with Limited Dispersion¹

Dr. Paul F McManamon
Air Force Research Laboratory
2224 Avionics Circle
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433
937-255-4039,ext 4024
Paul.McManamon@wpafb.af.mil

Dr. Edward A. Watson
Air Force Research Laboratory
2224 Avionics Circle
Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio 45433
937-255-4039,ext 4030
Edward.Watson@wpafb.af.mil

Abstract—This paper shows how the dispersion associated with optical phased array beam steering can be limited to moderate values of 20 to 80 times the diffraction limit even for very large angle beam steering. Much of the remaining factor of 20 – 80 may be correctable using digital techniques.¹

A significant obstacle associated with widespread implementation of optical phased array beam steering is the wavelength dispersion associated with resets.² In this paper we will discuss optical phased array beam steering using resets of greater than one wavelength. By using larger resets the unfolded phase front for wavelengths other than the design wavelength can be maintained closer to a prism, thus limiting dispersion. This technique can be implemented with the variable period beam steering approach and the variable blaze beam steering approach. One way to implement the variable blaze beam steering approach is using moveable lenslets.³ This method of implementation is amenable to large value resets, so it is an attractive method of implementation for this multiple wavelength reset, limited dispersion, beam steering

technique. By using resets of multiple wavelengths and limiting the dispersion we will be able to steer passive, broadband, electro-optical sensors over wide angles using optical phased array technology for the first time.

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1. INTRODUCTION

There are two basic approaches to beam steering using dynamic gratings.⁴ These approaches are apparent from consideration of the grating equation:

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$$\sin \theta = \frac{m\lambda}{A}, \quad (1)$$

where θ is the steering angle, m is the order of steering associated with the grating and λ is the wavelength of light and A is the period of the grating. One approach is to vary the period of the grating. In this approach the grating is usually blazed to effect steering to the first order, and the location of the orders, given by the grating equation, changes depending on the period. The other approach is to vary the blaze of the grating. In this case the location of the grating orders is constant, but the varying blaze results in energy being efficiently steered to different orders and hence different directions. Of interest to us here is the dispersion associated with beam steering. It is evident from the grating equation that the direction of steering is dependent on the wavelength. The dispersion can be determined by calculating the derivative of the steering angle with respect to wavelength. Differentiating Eq. (1) gives

$$\frac{d\theta}{d\lambda} = \frac{1}{\cos \theta} \left[\frac{dm}{d\lambda} \frac{\lambda}{A} + \frac{m}{A} \right]. \quad (2)$$

The derivative of the order m with respect to wavelength is taken because any of the orders will allow the diffracted wavefront to interfere constructively. Therefore, for selected wavelengths, the order to which they are steered may change but the absolute angle will remain the same. This can be seen from the term in brackets. If this term is zero, the dispersion will be zero. We note, however, that the variation in the grating order, dm , cannot be continuous. The grating order can only change in integer units. Therefore, the dispersion will be zero for only discrete wavelengths. For other wavelengths, the dispersion will be non-zero. However, it will be minimized by appropriate "choice" of the order m . That is, the light will naturally diffract into the order for which the dispersion is minimized.

To be formally correct when taking a derivative of m we should subscript it to refer to the m value with maximum intensity. All m

values are present and do not change, but the peak intensity m value is the one of interest here.

We now consider the magnitude of the dispersion for the two steering approaches.

2. VARIABLE PERIOD BEAM STEERING

Initially we consider the case of variable periods, as shown in Fig. 1. With variable period beam steering, as we move across the aperture the Optical Path Length (OPL) through the grating monotonically increases until it equals one wavelength of some "design" wavelength. Then we subtract one wavelength from the OPL. This is called a reset. This OPL can be generated using liquid crystal optical phased arrays.⁵ It could be implemented by other means as well, such as micromirrors. We could let the optical path length build up until we have any integer number of wavelengths of optical path delay, then do the reset. Since light is a sine wave, any integer number of wavelengths can be subtracted without influencing the unfolded phase front. The unfolded wavefront would then be a prism. Figure 2 shows an unfolded phase front for both the design wavelength and also an alternate wavelength. The OPL for the design wavelength and the alternate wavelength will be the same. The phase fronts for the two wavelengths will however be different. The reason is that at an alternate wavelength the OPL does not equal exactly one wavelength. The OPL is one wavelength at only the design wavelength. For example if the design wavelength is 1 μm , and the actual wavelength used is 1.1 μm , then we would build up to an OPL of 1 μm , then reset to zero. That is 327 degrees of phase for a 1.1 μm wavelength rather than the 360 degrees associated with a full wavelength of OPL.

Figure 1 Variable Period Beam Steering

Figure 3: Unfolded Phase Front for the design wavelength and an alternate wavelength

The unfolded phase ramp will then build to 327 degrees, then jump to 360 degrees. Each time a reset occurs there would be a 33-degree phase jump in the unfolded phase ramp. This will cause the beam energy to be steered into multiple grating lobes. In addition, from the grating equation we see that the longer wavelength will steer to a larger angle for a given order m . Even though a longer wavelength will steer to a larger angle, the blaze of the grating is for the steered angle at the design wavelength.

If we used a shorter wavelength of 0.9 μm we would build to 400 degrees phase shift, then reset to zero OPL, so the unfolded phase ramp would drop by 40 degrees of phase at each reset. At a shorter wavelength we steer to a smaller angle than the design wavelength, but again with the design wavelength blaze angle.

Now we consider the variable period approach, but using larger resets that are a multiple of the design wavelength rather than a reset of a single wavelength.

Figure 3: Variable Period resets with wavelength multiples

As can be seen, Fig. 3 and Fig. 1 are the same except both the spacing between resets and the amount of reset are multiplied by an integer factor of N . At wavelengths other than the design wavelength, however, there are differences between the cases of $N=1$ and $N>1$. The reason we look at the unfolded phase ramp is to determine if one ramp is in phase with the next ramp, or if there is a phase discontinuity that results in multiple grating orders receiving energy. In computing the unfolded phase ramp for the case of $N>1$, we can add $N(2\pi)$, or $(N-1)2\pi$, or $(N+1)2\pi$, or some other integer multiple of 2π . Obviously whatever multiple of 2π that results in the smallest phase discontinuity is the proper value to use in finding the unfolded phase ramp. This means there is less phase error in the unfolded phase ramp. The smallest unfolded phase jump possible is given by:

$$\phi = N * 2\pi - (\lambda_d / \lambda) * (N + p)2\pi \quad (3)$$

where N is a positive integer and p can be any positive or negative integer. Ideally we would like ϕ to be as close to zero as possible. However, ϕ will be zero for only a select set of discrete wavelengths since p can take on only discrete, integer values. Equation 3 shows flexibility to minimize the magnitude of the phase jumps both by having a large value of N and by picking the appropriate value of p .

Now we consider the effect on the direction of steering when resets of multiple 2π are employed. For a single 2π reset the change in angle resulting in operating at a wavelength other than the design wavelength is given by Eq. (4) (in the small angle approximation):

$$\Delta\theta_\lambda = \frac{\lambda}{A} - \frac{\lambda_d}{A} = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{A} \quad (4)$$

With multiple 2π resets the change in angle resulting from operating at other than the design wavelength is:

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{N\lambda_d}{NA} - \frac{(N+p)\lambda}{NA} = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{A} - \frac{p\lambda}{NA} \quad (5)$$

Comparing Eqs. (4) and (5) we can see that an additional term has been added which will allow us to minimize the dispersion in steering angle, and will allow the dispersion to be zero at certain discrete angles. As N becomes larger the magnitude of λ/NA decreases so that the increments of correction in Eq. (5) become finer.

We now consider an example. If we assume a design wavelength of $1 \mu\text{m}$ we can look at alternate wavelengths of $1.1 \mu\text{m}$ and $.9 \mu\text{m}$, as before. There are multiple approaches to unfold the phase delay. For example, if we use $N=10$, and a $1 \mu\text{m}$ design wavelength the OPL reset value is $10 \mu\text{m}$. For a wavelength of $1.1 \mu\text{m}$ and an N of 10 that amounts to 3272.7 degrees of phase, and for a wavelength of $.9 \mu\text{m}$ and an N of 10 that amounts to 4000 degrees of phase. The closest number of degrees divisible by 360 is 3240, or 9 times 360 for a wavelength of $1.1 \mu\text{m}$. This produces a phase discontinuity of 32.7 degrees at the reset rather than a phase discontinuity of 327.3 degrees. For $.9 \mu\text{m}$, 3960 degrees, or 11 times 360, is the closest integer number times 360, resulting in a phase discontinuity of 40 degrees rather than a phase discontinuity of 400 degrees. For both wavelengths the reduction in the magnitude of the phase resets are about an order of magnitude.

3. VARIABLE BLAZE BEAM STEERING

Next we consider variable blaze gratings as shown in Fig. 4. A variable blaze grating can be used to model the wavefront exiting a cascade of micro lens arrays.²

Figure 4: Variable Blaze Beam Steering

This type of grating can be modeled as follows. The phase variation ϕ that is imparted to a plane wave incident on a single period of the grating is given by the product of the wave number k times the *OPL* across a single period:

$$\phi = k \cdot OPL = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \frac{x}{B} N\lambda_0 \quad (6)$$

Where the coordinate x varies between zero and B , and where λ_0 is the design wavelength. This phase variation for a single period is then convolved with a sampling function to produce a periodic phase variation for the entire wavefront. A Fourier transform of this wavefront pattern will give the far field pattern, which can be written as

$$E \propto \text{sinc}\left(\frac{Bx}{\lambda R} - \frac{N\lambda_0}{\lambda}\right) \sum_m \delta\left(\frac{Bx}{\lambda R} - m\right), \quad (7)$$

where R is the distance to the far field plane and the terms in the sum describe the location of the grating orders. The sinc term describes the strength of the electric field in each of the grating orders.

As can be seen, this type of beam steering only directs energy to an order of the writable grating if the *OPL* is equal to a multiple of the wavelength. In that case one phase ramp is in phase with the next phase ramp. Otherwise we do not have constructive interference. The mainlobe will decrease and sidelobes will appear. The presence of side lobes is illustrated

in Fig. 5. This figure is plotted for the “worse case” in which an integral number of design wavelengths and an integral number of wavelengths under consideration differ by a factor of $\lambda/2$, that is

$$N\lambda_0 = L\lambda + \lambda/2, \quad (8)$$

where L is also an integer.

Figure 5: Far Field Pattern

As can be seen, for this case, all the orders of the grating receive some energy. As N becomes larger the pattern however becomes narrower. The angle we will steer to is again given by Eq. (1). Now, however, the order number m and the integer number N of wavelengths in the effective *OPL* are the same. As in the variable period case, wavelengths at other than the design wavelength can add in phase at other

integer values than N . Hence, in the small angle approximation, the dispersion in steering angle is given by

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{N\Delta\lambda}{B} + \frac{p\lambda}{B}, \quad (9)$$

where again p can be either a positive or negative number. Again we note that as B increases in magnitude, the ratio λ/B decreases so that the dispersion can be made smaller. We also have

$$\Delta\theta \leq \frac{\lambda}{2B} \quad (10)$$

as the largest angular dispersion possible in this case.

4. STEERING TO REAL ANGLES

Next we consider realistic steering angles. Table 1 shows errors resulting from steering across a wide bandwidth at a 10-degree design angle. It can be seen that the error created by steering off the design wavelength is

Table 1 Error Associated with Ten Degree Beam Steering and Large Resets
(Variable blaze beam steering)

λ_d (μm)	λ	B (mm)	θ_d (deg)	OPD,# of waves	θ deg	$\Delta\theta$ (deg)	$\Delta\theta$ (mrad)
1.00	1.00	1	10	176.00	9.9818	.018	.314
1.00	1.05	1	10	168.00	10.0041	-0.004	-0.0708
1.00	1.10	1	10	160.00	9.9818	0.018	0.3171
1.00	1.15	1	10	153.00	9.9791	0.021	0.3656
1.00	1.20	1	10	147.00	10.0041	-0.004	-0.0708
1.00	1.25	1	10	141.00	9.9957	0.004	0.0747
1.00	1.05	.2	10	34.00	10.1207	-0.121	-2.1067
1.00	1.10	.2	10	32.00	9.9818	0.018	0.3171
1.00	1.15	.2	10	31.00	10.1068	-0.107	-1.8644
1.00	1.20	.2	10	29.00	9.8706	0.129	2.2577
1.00	1.25	.2	10	28.00	9.9262	0.074	1.2873
4.00	6.00	1	10	29.00	9.8706	0.129	2.2577
4.00	4.50	1	10	39.00	9.9540	0.046	0.8022
4.00	3.50	1	10	50.00	9.9262	0.074	1.2873
4.00	3.00	1	10	59.00	10.0374	-0.037	-0.6527
4.00	4.00	1	10	44.00	9.9818	0.018	0.3171
4.00	5.00	.2	10	7.00	9.9262	0.074	1.2873
4.00	4.50	.2	10	8.00	10.2040	-0.204	-3.5600
4.00	3.50	.2	10	10.00	9.9262	0.074	1.2873
4.00	3.00	.2	10	12.00	10.2040	-0.204	-3.5600
4.00	4.00	.2	10	9.00	10.2040	-0.204	-3.5600

not large in either case, but it is much smaller for a 1 mm space between resets. A lenslet array with 0.2 or 1 mm spacing between resets should achieve the dispersion given in Table 1.

While this does involve some mechanical motion it would be no more than .5 mm, a small mechanical motion that should not be difficult to implement.

The error associated with steering to a 10-degree angle using the single wavelength reset approach is given in Table 2. In Table 1 we use fixed reset separations, so we cannot steer exactly to the design angle. In Table 2 we use Eq. (4), and calculate the correct OPL to direct energy to the design steering angle. In

comparing Tables 1 and 2 we see that there is orders of magnitude decrease in dispersion associated with steering a wavelength other than the design wavelength.

Table 2: Angular Error Resulting From Dispersion Using Single Wavelength Reset

λ_d (μm)	λ (μm)	θ_d (deg)	θ deg	$\Delta\theta$ (deg)	$\Delta\theta$ (mrad)
1	1.05	10	10.5	0.5	8.726646
1	1.1	10	11	1	17.45329
1	1.15	10	11.5	1.5	26.17994
1	1.2	10	12	2	34.90659
1	1.25	10	12.5	2.5	43.63323
4	5	10	12.5	2.5	43.63323
4	4.5	10	11.25	1.25	21.81662
4	3.5	10	8.75	-1.25	-21.8166
4	3	10	7.5	-2.5	-43.6332
4	4	10	10	0	0

Table 3: Ratio of Dispersion Between 2 Approaches

λ_d (μm)	λ (μm)	B (mm)	$\Delta\theta$ (deg)	$\Delta\theta$ (deg)	Improve Ratio
1	1.05	1	-0.004	0.5	-125.00
1	1.10	1	0.018	1	55.56
1	1.15	1	0.021	1.5	71.43
1	1.20	1	-0.004	2	-500.00
1	1.25	1	0.004	2.5	625.00
1	1.05	.2	-0.121	0.5	-4.13
1	1.10	.2	0.018	1	55.56
1	1.15	.2	-0.107	1.5	-14.02
1	1.20	.2	0.129	2	15.50
1	1.25	.2	0.074	2.5	33.78
4	6.00	1	0.129	2.5	19.38
4	4.50	1	0.046	1.25	27.17
4	3.50	1	0.074	-1.25	-16.89
4	3.00	1	-0.037	-2.5	67.57
4	4.00	1	0.018	0	0.00
4	5.00	.2	0.074	2.5	33.78
4	4.50	.2	-0.204	1.25	-6.13
4	3.50	.2	0.074	-1.25	-16.89
4	3.00	.2	-0.204	-2.5	12.25
4	4.00	.2	-0.204	0	0.00

The angular error associated with conventional resets, and this classic equation, are shown in Table 2. One thing that is not shown in the tables is very important. **Using the blazed approach we find the dispersion to be essentially independent of steering angle.** This is because larger steering angles imply a larger OPL before reset and therefore more reduction in the total dispersion. Small angle correction techniques used for limited dispersion should therefore apply and may be able to eliminate the remaining dispersion.

5. STEERING PASSIVE SENSORS

One measure of the merit of a sensor is how close it is to the diffraction limit. We can use Eq. (10) and compare it to the diffraction limit to consider how well this correction technique has corrected for diffraction. The diffraction limit is approximately given by⁶:

$$\Delta\theta_{dif} = \frac{1.2\lambda}{D} \quad (11)$$

Where D is the aperture diameter and we use a factor of 1.2 for the width of the beam at the first zero in the diffraction pattern. Taking the ratio between equation 10 and 11 we have:

$$\frac{\Delta\theta_{max}}{\Delta\theta_{dif}} \leq \frac{D}{2.4B} \quad (12)$$

We can see that how far we are from the diffraction limit depends on the ratio of the lenslet size to the full aperture size. Wavelength has dropped out of the equation. If we have a 5 cm diameter aperture and 1 mm lenslets we are about a factor of 20 from diffraction limited. With a 20 cm aperture and 1 mm lenslets we are about a factor of 80 away from the diffraction limit. Equation 12 lets us see that the number of lenslet sub apertures divided by about two and a half is the ratio how far the sensor is from the diffraction limit. With sensors only a factor of 20 to 80 away from the diffraction limit digital

approaches to generate the angle / angle / wavelength image cube by dithering the image aim point and using processing should be very promising. Since it is a constant amount of dispersion vs. angle it will also make it much easier to use this approach for multi or hyperspectral passive sensors.

6. CONCLUSIONS

We have shown a dramatic reduction of optical phased array dispersion by using resets that are many multiples of a single wavelength. The lenslet approach to optical phased array beam steering is a variable blaze approach that is an ideal method of creating large resets, and limiting dispersion. Large resets occur naturally for large period lenslets, resulting in approximately constant dispersion verse angle, even for large angle beam steering. We have less dispersion if the period between resets is larger, for example 1 mm rather than 200 μm . This technique should allow non-mechanical beam steering for passive sensors as well as for laser sensing. It may be especially valuable for multi or Hyperspectral passive sensing.

BIOGRAPHIES

Paul F. McManamon received his Ph.D. in Physics from Ohio State University in 1977. He has worked at Wright Patterson AFB since 1968, joining Wright laboratory in 1979. His Ph.d was in laser physics. His primary work at in the laboratory has been in electro-optical sensors. He was primary author a paper entitled "Optical Phased Array Technology" that received the IEEE W.R.J. Baker award for the best paper in any IEEE referred journal or transaction. Recently he has emphasized laser radar sensors more than passive IR/EO sensors,

but has research interests in both areas. He acted as Chief Scientist for the Avionics Directorate of Wright Lab for over two and a half years. He is currently senior scientist for Infrared Sensors, working in the Sensors Directorate of the Air Force Research Laboratory. He is a Senior member of IEEE and a Fellow of SPIE.

Ed Watson is the Technical Advisor for the Electro-Optical Technology Division, Sensors Directorate, Air Force Research Laboratory. He conducts research in active and passive electro-optic sensors, including the application of

dynamic diffractive optical components to the agile steering and shaping of monochromatic and polychromatic light beams, development of multi-phenomenology laser radar imagers, and modeling of aliasing and blurring in sampled imagery. He has a Ph. D. in Optics from the University of Rochester, and an M. S. degree in Optical Sciences and a B. S. degree in Physics from the University of Arizona.

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